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FINANCIAL DERIVATIVE AND THE PERFORMANCE OF LISTED BANKS IN NIGERIA WITH INTERNATIONAL AUTHORIZATION

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of financial derivatives on financial performance in Nigeria drawing samples from commercial banks quoted on the floor of the Nigerian stock exchange market. While financial performance proxy of Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) was the dependent variable, the independent variables that was adopted for this study includes financial derivative of assets (FDAS) and financial derivatives of liabilities (FDL). Furthermore, the study employed the variable of debt to asset ratio to control the model's goodness of fit. The writer employed all twelve (12) quoted banks in Nigeria (Central Bank of Nigeria CBN 2020) as of December 31st, 2020. However due to the nature of this study where the writer needed to employ cross section (sample banks) that possess similar characteristics and attributes the writer limits the population of this study to eight (8) quoted commercial banks that have international categorization classification. To test the hypotheses of the study, the quantile regression technique was employed. Overall, the study concluded that the results obtained from the study showed that financial derivative has significant effect on performance of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. But it should be noted that the effect is conditional on the performance level (quantile) of the firm. In view of the findings obtained from the regression analyses the writer carefully recommended that corporate managers especially those within the banking sector should engage/drive policies that will promote the use of derivative liabilities against the use of derivative assets. This is in response to the negative effect which the variable of derivative asset has on firm performance.

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INTRODUCTION

In this era of globalization, business competition related to investment and funding has become very complex. Alternative financial instruments are increasingly developing in line with the development of investment and funding. Along with more profitable offers, investors begin to move their investment portfolios to other companies. The key to a company is to maintain its investors, both shareholders, debt holders, and other stakeholders are by constantly creating and realizing the value of the company. The role of the company's value is very large because the value of the company is a consideration of the

level of success of the company; [Shapiro \(2013\)](#). The high value of the firm will lead to market confidence that not only trusts the company's current performance, but also the prospects of the company. Every financial transaction entered by market participants are constantly and inevitably exposed to different forms of risks: credit risks, interest rate risks, currency/foreign exchange risks, commodity risks, systemic risks, operational risks to mention but a few. Specifically, almost all companies (especially companies that are international in scale) activities are connected to the international market circuit consequently exposing the company's cash flow to changes in exchange rates.

This makes the use of derivative activities taking the form of hedging very necessary. Financial derivative is one hedging technique used in protecting firms from financial risks. They are employed for a number of purposes, such as hedging against future price movements of securities or against speculation or getting to trade assets or market. Some of the common derivatives include; forwards, futures, options and swaps. According to [Putro \(2012\)](#), derivatives are financial contracts where the value comes from the underlying assets. This means that derivative instruments are financial instruments whose value depends or is derived from the underlying assets. But on the flip side, [Buffett \(2002\)](#), referred to them as “financial weapons of mass destruction”. Noting that reckless use of financial derivative instruments for speculative purposes automatically creates new risks. Financial derivatives have grown so much in popularity that they are also regarded as asset classes, although they most often derive their values from one or more underlying security that may belong to different asset classes. As [Buffett \(2002\)](#), pointed out, they are sometimes embedded in new investment vehicles of debt and equities, which is typically one of the reasons why the complexities of these instruments make them highly risky.

The connectivity between financial derivatives and firm's performance is abundant in a wide array of research works. The studies mentioned below have generally found mixed evidences. For instance, financial derivatives reduce the impact of credit worthiness of companies and reduce monetary policy transmissions; [Fender \(2000\)](#). Financial derivative hedging significantly reduces systematic risk, create larger profits and give abnormal returns to nonfinancial firms; [Bartram Brown and Conrad \(2016\)](#); the use of options derivative trading increases innovative productivity and short-term performance; [Blanco and Wehrheim \(2015\)](#). [Stoll and Whaley \(2010\)](#), argued that the use of derivative offer the firm with financial benefits, and the main contribution of these derivatives are their leverages. Which means, for a given purchasing cost of the underlying asset they produce similar price exposure with that of the owners. Consequently, they deliver a competent means of counterbalancing between hedgers (those risk transferors) and speculators which were also found to be similar with the findings of [MacCarthy \(2017\)](#), [Guney, Ahmed & Azevedo \(2014\)](#). On the other hand, [Allayannisand & Weston \(2012\)](#), [Akun \(2016\)](#), documented a negative effect of financial derivatives on firm's financial performance amongst quoted companies.

Although information on firm's financial derivative usage is widely available in the developed world, empirical research regarding whether the use of derivative will increase financial performance of a company is still subject of debate especially in a developing country like Nigeria. Therefore, the need for effective management of financial derivatives stands as fundamental to performance of firms in the financial services sector in Nigeria. In view of this development, this study sets out to look at the effect of financial derivatives on financial performance of listed banks in Nigeria. The study extend the work of others in checking how the use of financial derivatives has improved firm's performance across the

period 2013—2020. More so, it will add to existing knowledge in corporate finance, and will be valuable to the regulators like the Capital Markets Authority, Central Bank of Nigeria and Nigerian Bankers Association who can employ this study's findings, recommendations and conclusions to enact and improve regulations and operation procedures of financial derivatives in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Firm's Performance

This is a test of how properly a firm can utilize its assets from its essential business operations to create incomes. Financial performance is typically utilized as a measure of the general financial health of a firm throughout a particular time period. Banks assume a critical part in allocating the country's economic resource as they continuously direct funds from the depositors to investors. Banks need to be profitable in order to ensure sustainable intermediation function. Good financial performance ensures that the shareholders are rewarded for their investment. This motivates them to bring in additional investments that lead to economic growth. Poor banking performance on the other hand result in banking crisis and failure that have negative impact on the economic growth. According to [Toutou \(2011\)](#), financial performance is a general measure of how well a bank generates revenues from its capital. It also shows a bank's overall financial health over a period of time, and it helps to compare different banks across the banking industry at the same time. The bank's financial performance generally can be recognized as its stability and profitability. The stability refers to its risk factors and profitability refers to its financial return.

Financial Derivative

[McDonald \(2013\)](#) defines financial derivatives as a financial instrument that has its value derived and determined from or by the price and performance of something else. The term financial derivative was similarly defined by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) as a 'financial instrument that is linked to a specific financial instrument, indicator or commodity and through which specific financial risks can be traded in financial markets. Simply put, financial derivative is a contract and the value of that contract is often derived from the performance of anything the parties to the contract choose and call the 'underlying' asset. The assets from which a derivative contract derives its value, in other words; the 'underlying' could be equity (i.e. stock or stock index), fixed-income instrument (which include treasury bonds or notes), commodities (such as gold, silver, crude oil, wheat, rice, to mention but a few), interest rates (for example, London Inter-bank Offered Exchange Rate, EURIBOR- Euro Inter-Bank Offered Rate, NIBOR- Nigerian Inter-Bank Offered Rate), foreign currency, etc. It is these underlying assets that derivatives draw its value from.

Financial Derivative Assets

Derivative assets are those trading or non-hedging derivative such as forward, future, options and swaps contracts that the firm acquires or incurs for the purpose of selling or purchasing in the near term or holds as part of a portfolio that is managed together for short-term profit or position taking. They are initially recognized and subsequently measured at fair value in the statement of financial position. Fair values are obtained from quoted market prices in active markets, including recent market transactions, and valuation techniques. Derivatives are carried as assets when their fair values are positive. [Grant \(2017\)](#) stated that derivative assets are not hard physical assets, but contracts that have a defined and specified life span. They are traded in world financial

markets among buyers and sellers who are betting on the future price of the underlying assets that are represented by the derivatives.

Financial Derivative Liabilities

Derivative liabilities are those trading or non-hedging derivatives such as forwards, futures, options and swaps contracts that the firm acquires or incurs for the purpose of selling or purchasing in the near term or holds as part of a portfolio that is managed together for short-term profit or position taking. They are initially recognized and subsequently measured at fair value in the statement of financial position. Fair values are obtained from quoted market prices in active markets, including recent market transactions, and valuation techniques. Derivatives are carried as liabilities when their fair values are negative. Grant (2017) stated that derivative liabilities are financial instruments under contracts that have one or more underlying and one or more notional amounts. Fair values as of the balance sheet date of all liabilities resulting from contracts that meet the criteria of being accounted for as derivative instruments, and which are expected to be extinguished or otherwise disposed of within a year or the normal operating cycle, if longer, net of the effects of master netting arrangements.

Theoretical Framework

The Modern Portfolio Theory of Investment

The Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) is an improvement upon traditional investment models. It is an important advancement in the mathematical modeling of finance. The MPT encourages asset diversification to hedge against market risk as well as risk that is unique to a specific company. The theory is a sophisticated investment decision approach that aids an investor to classify, estimate, and control both the kind and the amount of expected risk and return; also called Portfolio Management Theory (PMT). Essential to the portfolio theory are its quantifications of the relationship between risk and return and the assumption that investors must be compensated for taking risk. The Modern Portfolio Theory (MPT) departs from traditional security analysis in shifting emphasis from analyzing the characteristics of individual investments to determining the statistical relationships among the individual securities that comprise the overall portfolio, Elton & Gruber (1997). The MPT mathematically formulates the concept of diversification in investing, with the aim of selecting a collection of investment assets that has collectively lower risk than any individual asset. The possibility of this can be seen intuitively because different types of assets often change in value in opposite ways.

Empirical Review

Ekadjaja and Henny (2019), examines the characteristics of user's derivative company towards the company's value. The population of this study are all companies listed in the Sharia Stock Index on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in 2014-2016. Multiple linear regression analysis is used to test the hypothesis. The result of the test showed that Return on Asset and firm size variables have a significant positive effect on the firm's value of derivative users. While capital expenditure and dividend yield showed no significant effect on firm's value and the leverage variable showed a significant negative effect on firm's value.

Osayi, et al. (2018), examined the effects of the use of financial market derivatives on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study utilized data covering five years and employed descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and regression analysis to determine the relationship between the variables in the study. The findings revealed that,

there is a positive relationship between derivative financial assets and the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Hence, the study concluded that the use of derivative is of immense importance to the performance of banks in Nigeria.

MacCarthy (2017) investigated the impact of financial derivatives on the performance of firms in the financial sector in Ghana. Secondary data on financial derivatives, controlled business risks and business performance in terms of return on investment were used for the period 2011-2015. Data were sourced from 23 randomly selected financial firms in Accra, Ghana. A quantitative research technique is used to test four hypotheses. A strong positive correlation between financial derivatives and controlled business risks is found. Also, there is a strong positive correlation between financial derivatives and business performance in Ghana.

Joseph and Jagong (2017) investigated the influence of financial risk hedging practices on the performance of firms in Nigeria stock exchange (NSE). The study applied both descriptive and inferential statistics to analyse collected quantitative data. In descriptive analysis, the study used the mean and standard deviation to measure the average distribution and variation, respectively. The inferential statistics employed the use of multiple regression model. The regression model enabled the researcher to analyze the variation in performance caused by the use of futures, forwards, options or swaps to hedge on foreign exchange, interest rate and commodity price risks. Data on return on invested capital (ROIC) and return on assets (ROA) was collected from the firm's financial statements for 2011-2015. The study established a positive relationship between hedging practices, the moderator (central bank controls) and performance of listed firms.

Altuntas, et al. (2017) explored the relation between hedging, cash flows, and firm's value. Specifically, the study assessed the impact of derivatives hedging on firm's value both directly and indirectly through its effect on cash flow volatility. The study found that both derivatives hedging and cash flow volatility are negatively related to firm's value. Overall, the study found that derivative usage alone decreases firm value and performance. However, when the study evaluated the impact of hedging through cash flow volatility, the firms' value of the hedgers was found to be less sensitive to cash flow volatility compared to the value of non-hedgers.

Hypotheses Development

Derivatives Assets and Corporate Performance

Nowadays, all firms are well aware of derivatives as they are using them in risk management and speculative reasons. For this, firms' financial statements have been showing a gradual change in the employment of these derivatives and reporting them with disclosure required by international financial reporting standards (IFRS 9) financial instrument; Graham & Rogers (2016). The awareness was specially developed since 2008-2009 global crisis which left its mark on the world economy, and many countries are still struggling from the injury. Then after, scholars also have given attention towards investigation of derivatives' role in world economic crisis and devoting much effort in finding ways on how firms can tackle similar situation in the future. On the other view, firms, which stand for profit making objectives, are working hard to ensure their sustainability, Ilyina (2004). This means that they are involved in a kind of business operation, which makes their stakeholders satisfied from the services provided or products delivered to them. In return, the firms expect some kind of loyalty, long-lasting business relationships among others, Grant (2017). Gaining these factors help the firm in pledging competitive advantages that

lead to better performance results, which contribute to the increase in firm's value. Firms, which are operating both in financial and non-financial markets, are facing a tougher competition. On this, the major concern is related to the firm's value, which is how much a given firm is worth at the current market pool. In securing this, firms look for something unique and apply innovative products and services to bet the market. However, this requires a continuous process, and it is also riskier because markets are experiencing fast inflow of newly innovated products and services. On the basis of the above, the first hypothesis of the study is stated as

H0₁: Financial derivative asset has no significant effect on the performance of listed banks in Nigeria

Derivative Liabilities and Corporate Performance

Tsetsekos and Varangis (1997) indicated that commercial banks that utilize derivative assets can face less uncertainty in interest rates and thus increase their lending activities which then lead to higher returns compared to the fixed fee for service activities return. This is possible if the interest rate risk can be managed using derivatives. The total gain of commercial banks that utilise derivatives assets to control uncertainty in interest rates would therefore be higher than those that do not. According to Tsetsekos and Varangis (2017); Ilyina (2017), the use of derivatives can promote financial risk exposure management because they enable investors to transfer and unbundle financial risk. Stern and Linan (2018), and Jason & Taylor (2018), indicated that derivative trading for the purpose of profit is very risky and can subject the firm to large amount of losses and as stated by the study conducted by Ilyina (2017), derivative contracts have developed rapidly from uncomplicated financial futures to a broad range of complex and exotic securities all over the world. Derivative instruments have increasingly become a crucial part of commercial banks portfolio of assets that they use to mitigate their interest and foreign exchange rate risk exposure. As volatility of interest rates continues to increase, commercial banks have acknowledged the benefits of interest rate swaps and futures in decreasing risk and attaining optimal financial performance. On the basis of the above, the second hypothesis of the study is stated as

H0₂: Financial derivative liabilities has no significant effect on the performance of listed banks in Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

In this study, the writer adopted both the descriptive and ex-post research designs. The descriptive design was used since it best describes specific behaviour as it occurs in the environment. Furthermore, the choice of descriptive research design was on the basis that it allows a researcher to determine the correlations among several variables; Cooper & Schindler (2020). However, the ex-post facto research design was hinged on two major reasons: Firstly, the study will rely on historic accounting data obtained from financial statements of the sampled companies; hence the researcher did not control or manipulate the data of the study variables which was a basic feature of ex-post facto research design. Secondly, the ex-post facto research design was adopted for this study since the study's intention was to determine cause-effect relationships between the independent and dependent variables with a view to establishing a causal link between them. In this study, the writers employed all twelve (12) quoted banks in Nigeria (Central Bank of Nigeria CBN 2020) as of December 31st, 2020. However due to the nature of this study where cross section needed to be employed (sample banks) that possess similar characteristics and

attributes we limited the population of this study to eight (8) quoted commercial banks that have been categorized as international licensed banks following Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN 2020) classification. This selection procedure allows the researcher to eliminate commercial banks with national, regional authorization, non-interest taking commercial banks and merchant banks during the period under consideration.

In the data analysis process, the researcher first introduced the estimation technique of quantile regression in brief. The contention here is that standard least squares regression techniques provide summary point estimates that calculate the average effect of the independent variables on the 'average company'. However, this focus on the average company may hide important features of the underlying relationship. As Mosteller and Tukey (2019) correctly argued, "What the regression curve does is to give a grand summary for the averages of the distributions corresponding to the set of x's. But the researcher could go further and compute several regression curves corresponding to various percentage points of the distributions and thus get a more accurate picture of the set. Ordinarily, the Ordinary Least Square Regression curve cannot do this since it often gives a rather incomplete picture. Just as the mean gives an incomplete picture of a single distribution, so the regression curve gives a correspondingly incomplete picture for a set of distributions. However, Quantile regression techniques can help the research obtain a more complete picture of the underlying relationship between financial derivative and firm performance. In this case, estimation of linear models by quantile regression is preferable to the usual Ordinary Least Square regression method. Furthermore, due to the advantages of quantile regression estimation technique over the ordinary least square regression, fixed and random effect models, the researcher examined the variants of financial derivative holding at 25th, 50th, and 90th quantiles due to their popular usage and unique advantages in prior research as shown by Callistus et al (2010).

$$Q_{.25}ROCE_{it} = \lambda_{.25,0} + \lambda_{.25,1}FDAS_{it} + \lambda_{.25,2}FDLB_{it} + \lambda_{.25,3}DETA_{it} + \mu_{25it}$$

$$Q_{.50}ROCE_{it} = \lambda_{.50,0} + \lambda_{.50,1}FDAS_{it} + \lambda_{.50,2}FDLB_{it} + \lambda_{.50,3}DETA_{it} + \mu_{50it}$$

$$Q_{.90}ROCE_{it} = \lambda_{.90,0} + \lambda_{.90,1}FDAS_{it} + \lambda_{.90,2}FDLB_{it} + \lambda_{.90,3}DETA_{it} + \mu_{90it}$$

Where:

ROCE = Return on Capital Employed

FDAS = Financial Derivative of Assets

FDLB = Financial Derivative of Liability

DETA = Debt to Asset Ratio

i = individual cross section (quoted banks) and t = time

Q.25, Q.50 Q.90 = Quantile 25, Quantile .50 and Quantile 90

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study evaluated the effect of financial derivatives on financial performance in Nigeria drawing samples from eight (8) commercial banks quoted on the floor of the Nigerian stock exchange market. While financial performance proxy of Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) was the dependent variable, the independent variables that the researcher adopted for this study were financial derivative of asset (FDAS) and financial derivatives of liabilities (FDLB).

Furthermore, the study employed the variable of debt to asset ratio to control the model's goodness of fit.

Descriptive Statistics

The table below shows the descriptive statistics of this study, and it is discussed below.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and the Effect of Financial Derivative on Financial Performance

VARIABLES	MEAN	SD	MIN	MAX	NO OBS
ROCE	2.05	1.33	0.36	6.36	64
FDAS	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.05	64
FDLB	0.00	0.00	-0.00	0.02	64
DETA	82.48	17.33	-16.81	91.31	64

Source: Author (2022)

The table above shows the summary of the descriptive statistics of the study. From the table it is observed that financial performance as measured in terms of return on capital employed (ROCE) had a mean of 2.05 and a standard deviation of 1.33. In the case of the control variable, the table shows that financial derivative of asset (FDAS) had a mean of 0.01 with a standard deviation of 0.01. Financial derivative of liabilities (FDLB) had a mean of 0.00 and a standard deviation of 0.00. In the case of the control variable, the table shows that the mean of debt to asset ratio (DETA) was 82.48 and a standard deviation of 17.33.

Correlation Analysis

The study employed the Spearman Rank Correlation technique to conduct the possible association among the variables of interest shown in the table below.

Table 2: Correlation analysis of the effect of financial derivative on financial performance

	ROCE	FDAS	FDLB	DETA
ROCE	1.00			
FDAS	0.38	1.00		
FDLB	0.34	0.63	1.00	
DETA	-0.24	0.07	-0.10	1.00

Author's Computation (2022)

From the result displayed in table 2 above, the researcher found all the independent variables of derivative asset (0.38) and derivative liabilities (0.34) had a positive association with the dependent variable of return on capital employed (ROCE). However, the researcher found a negative association between the control variables of debt to asset ratio (-0.24) and the dependent variable of return on capital employed (ROCE) during the period under investigation.

Quantile Regression Analysis

The study presents below a summarized result obtained from the Quantile Regression Analyses Technique in a bid to find the possible effect of financial derivative on firm performance of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria for the period ranging from 2013 to 2020 fiscal years.

Table 3: Quantile Regression Result of Financial Derivative on Financial Performance

	Derivative Asset	Derivative Liabilities	Leverage
ROCE Model			
Q25			
Coefficient	2.232	46.633	-0.019
t_Statistics	(0.15)	(1.07)	(-2.44)
Probability_t	{0.880}	{0.291}	{0.019**}
Numb. Obs. = 64	Pseudo R² = 0.2303		
Q50			
Coefficient	-12.032	27.395	-0.018
t_Statistics	(-0.55)	(0.42)	(-1.56)
Probability_t	{0.584}	{0.675}	{0.127}
Numb. Obs. = 64	Pseudo R² = 0.2065		
Q90			
Coefficient	-75.731	136.189	-0.017
t_Statistics	(-2.99)	(1.81)	(-1.28)
Probability_t	{0.004**}	{0.077}	{0.208}
Numb. Obs. = 64	Pseudo R² = 0.4127		

Note: t-statistics and respective probabilities are represented in () and {}

*Where: ** represents 5% & * represent 1% level of significance*

Source: Authors' Computations via Stata 15 (2020)

The table above shows the summary of the results obtain from the 25th quantile, 50th quantile as well as the 90th quantile of the return on capital employed model. From the table, the pseudo R² of the 25th quantile (0.23), 50th quantile (0.21) and 90th quantile (0.41) indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable of return on capital employed that is predictable from the independent variables. It therefore implies that about 23%, 21% and 41% (for the respective quantiles) of the variation in the dependent variable was predictable by all the independent and control variables in the model. It also meant that about 77%, 79% and 59% of the variation in the dependent variable was left unpredictable but captured in the error term. Thus, from the foregoing, the researcher found the model fit for interpretation and for policy recommendation.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the return on capital employed (ROCE) model, we obtained the results for the variable of derivative asset as; (coefficient = 2.232, t = 0.15, p-value = 0.880) for 25th quantile, (coefficient = -12.032, t = -0.55, p-value = 0.584) for 50th quantile and (coefficient = -75.731, t = -2.99, p-value = 0.004) for 90th quantile. This indicates that at the lowest (25th) quantiles there is a positive insignificant effect of derivative asset on performance of commercial banks in our sample. Furthermore, there is a negative insignificant effect of derivative asset on the performance of the banks in our sample at the middle (50th) quantile. However, at the highest quantile (90th), the researcher found a negative significant effect of derivative asset on performance of the banks in our sample. This result is inconsistent with the stated null hypotheses leading to its rejection. Therefore, derivative asset has a significant effect on performance of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria. However, this is obtainable only at the highest quantile of the study.

This finding is consistent with the position of Hagelin et al. (2007) who concluded that firm performance decreases when a firm involve in hedging activates on the motive of manager's stock options. As a firm utilizes derivatives to reduce stock price sensitivity of

managerial stock option, hedging reduces firm performance. This reduction in firm performance is due to managers who usually hold risk avert motives and protect their claim on firm's assets due to stock options they hold. Our finding also supports those of [Fauver & Naranjo \(2010\)](#), who employed the perspective of agency costs and monitoring problems. In their remarks, they noted that firms with a huge amount of agency and monitoring problem like; low transparent, significant agency costs and information asymmetry problem, weaker corporate governance and monitoring, are subject to have negative correlation between performance and derivative usage.

For the variable of derivative liability, the result obtained from return on capital employed model is as follows: (coefficient = 46.633, $t = 1.07$, $p\text{-value} = 0.291$) for 25th quantile, (coefficient = 27.395, $t = 0.42$, $p\text{-value} = 0.675$) for 50th quantile and (coefficient = 136.189, $t = 1.81$, $p\text{-value} = 0.077$) for 90th quantile. This indicates that at the lowest (25th), middle (50th), and the highest (90th) quantiles there is a positive insignificant effect of derivative liability on performance of commercial banks in our sample. This result is inconsistent with the stated null hypotheses leading to its rejection. Therefore, derivative liability has a significant effect on performance of quoted commercial banks in Nigeria. The results implied that the use of derivative liabilities reduces the performance level of quoted commercial banks (specifically international licensed banks) in Nigeria. More specifically, the analyses revealed that the effect of derivative liability usage on firm performance is conditional on the performance level which the firm is operating at hence the use of quantile regression analyses technique is justified. In this study, we find that the positive significant condition will hold only at 90th quantile of the performance distribution. This finding is consistent with similar outcome of [Smith et al. \(1993\)](#) who concluded that firms which use derivative in risk management show more growth opportunities and more convex tax function compared to that of non-users. Similarly, the researcher aligned his result with those of [Geczy et al. \(1997\)](#), who concluded that firms in higher growth options, wide exposure to foreign exchange rate, tough financial restrains, and economies of scale in hedging activities, were found more likely to use foreign currency derivatives.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Derivatives help to alter international transmission by making arbitrage less expensive to reduce transactional transmission by making use of market size. The rationale behind the use of derivatives is that, by lowering transaction costs, it increases liquidity period. Financial derivatives compared with equivalent transaction in underlying assets derivatives can reduce the occurrence of large funds. On this premise, we conducted an analysis to empirically test the effect of financial derivative on performance of listed commercial banks that falls within the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) class of internationally licensed commercial banks in Nigeria. From the results we find that the effect of financial derivative usage on firm performance produces mixed results. Overall, the study concludes that the results obtained from the study showed that financial derivative has significant effect on performance of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the effect is conditional on the performance level (quantile) of the firm. In view of the findings obtained from the regression analyses we carefully recommend that corporate managers especially those within the banking sector should engage/drive policies that will promote the use of derivative liabilities against the use of derivative assets. This is in response to the negative effect which the variable of derivative asset has on firm performance.

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